

Classical Mechanics, Galilean Transformations and Hint of Special Relativity?

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In (1) a Galilean transformation $x' = x - vt$ and $t' = t$ is applied to the Schrodinger equation $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x,t)$ for a free particle, where $W(x,t)$ is the wavefunction, and it is argued that $W'(x',t')$ does not equal $W(x(x',t'),t(x',t'))$. Instead it is shown that $W'(x',t') = W(x,t) \exp(-i/\hbar [mvx' + .5mvvt'])$ with $x = x' + vt'$ and $t = t'$. The author's of (1) suggest this is due to remnants of special relativity creeping into the nonrelativistic situation. They then argue that this issue is already found in nonrelativistic classical mechanics, in particular in the Hamiltonian-Jacobi equation $H(x, dS/dx) + dS/dt = 0$ where S is the free particle action = t *Lagrangian and H is the Hamiltonian i.e $1/2m dS/dx dS/dx$. They show that $S'(x',t') = S(x,t) - (mvx' + .5mvvt')$ and also argue that this is due to a remnant of special relativity creeping into nonrelativistic classical mechanics.

In this note, we consider the free particle action $S = -Et + px$ nonrelativistically. (This form also holds for the relativistic free particle). It may be seen that such a solution satisfies the Hamilton-Jacobi equation, but the catch seems to be that one must transform both (x,t) and (p,E) to find a solution in a moving frame. The Galilean transformation leads to two different transformations, one for (x,t) and another for (p,E) . A Lorentz transformation on the other hand treats (x,t) and (p,E) in the same way and $-Et + px$ behaves as a dot product with a $(1,-1)$ type metric. We argue that given the physical example of a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=0$, a moving frame transforms this into a new energy (including m_0 and kinetic energy), a p and x',t' such that $x'/t' = v$ where $-v$ is the velocity of the frame. One may suggest a more general transformation than the Galilean i.e. replace $t' = t$ with $t' = g(v) t$. This then leads to $-Et + px$ written in terms of E',t', p',x' equalling $-E't' + p'x'$ if $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/bb}$ where b is a constant to make v/b dimensionless. Applying the transformation, which we assume holds for both (x,t) and (p,E) to light yields $b=c$.

One may then show that $-Et + px$, written in terms of E',t',p',x' , yields $-E't' + p'x'$,

Remnants of Special Relativity in the Schrodinger Equation and Hamilton Jacobi Equation from (1)

In (1) the Schrodinger equation together with a Galilean transformation $x' = x - vt$ and $t' = t$ is considered. In particular, $W(x,t) = W(x' + vt', t')$ is inserted into the Schrodinger equation in x',t' variables and it may be seen immediately that it is not a solution. Next a solution of the form $W(x,t) \exp(i f(x',t'))$ may be tried so that it has unit modulus. This leads to:

$$i \frac{d}{dt'} \{W(x,t) \exp(i f(x',t'))\} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx'^2} \{W(x,t) \exp(i f(x',t'))\} \text{ or}$$

$$i \frac{d}{dt'} W(x,t) |x \text{ constant} - p v - i W \frac{df}{dt'} \text{ partial} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x,t) + \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx'} \frac{d}{dx'} f + p/m \frac{df}{dx} \text{ partial}$$

An immediate solution is $f(x',t') = .5mvv t' + mv x'$

The authors of (1) ascribe the extra phase $f(x',t')$ to remnants of special relativity. They then go on to show that these remnants appear in the nonrelativistic classical mechanical Hamilton Jacobi equation:

$H(x, dS/dx \text{ partial}) + dS/dt = 0$ where $S = \text{Lagrangian} * t$ i.e. the Action

They argue that the remnants follow in two ways:

(A) By performing a Galilean transformation

(B) By taking the solution $-.5mv^2 t + mv x$ and insisting that v transform as $v' = v - v_1$.

For a free particle $H = 1/2m (dS/dx)^2 + dS/dt$. As a result, they argue that special relativistic remnants already exist in nonrelativistic classical mechanical theory.

Quantum Mechanics and the Hamilton-Jacobi Equation

In (1) it is argued that the Schrodinger equation for a free particle with the Galilean transformation leads to extra terms in a phase. These are the same extra terms which appear in a Hamilton-Jacobi nonrelativistic classical mechanical treatment. A solution for the Hamiltonian Jacobi equation is $-Et + px$ as noted in (1) and the free particle Schrodinger equation solution as not explicitly mentioned in (1) is $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ where $E = .5mv^2$ and $p = mv$. In fact, the Hamilton Jacobi equation is almost identical to the Schrodinger equation except that it does not use $\exp(iS)$, but S itself. Thus issues with the Galilean transformation in the Schrodinger equation will automatically have their counterpart in the Hamilton Jacobi classical equation as noted in (1).

Action = $m/2 (xx/t)$ Considerations With Only x, t and m Appearing

One may obtain the results of (1) for the nonrelativistic classical case by using $v = x/t$ so that one does not need to worry about how v transforms i.e. scenario (B) described above from (1).

Action = $Lt = m/2 (xx/t)$ ((1))

Then $m/2 (x'x'/t') = m/2 \{ (x'+vt')(x'+vt')/t' \} = m/2 (x'x'/t't') + m/2 \{ 2vx + vt^2 \}$ ((2))

The second term in $\{ \}$ on the RHS is the extra factor given in (1).

Action = -Et+px Considerations

Consider $S(x,t) = -Et+px$ with $t=t'$ and $x=x'+vt'$: Then

$$S(x'+vt', t') = -E' t' + p' x' + (mvx' + m/2 vv t') \quad \text{where } E' = m/2 (v1-v)(v1-v) \text{ and } p' = m (v1-v)$$

$$\text{And } E=m/2 v1v1, p=m v1 \text{ and } -E't' + p'x' = S'(x',t')$$

Thus one quickly obtains the extra terms listed in (1) as done in (1) (B). Thus there seems to be a problem with the Galilean transformation, even at a nonrelativistic classical mechanical level.

The form $-Et+px$ has the appearance of a dot product with a new metric of the form (1,-1). It is not only x,t which transform, but p,E . In the Galilean transformation scenario, one only thinks of $v1$ (velocity in x,t) transforming to $v1-v$. Alternatively, one may think in terms of p,E as variables which transform. It would be interesting to have one transformation which applies to both sets. The Galilean transformation treats x,t differently from $v1$ and differently from p,E . This seems to be its problem (in particular treating p,E changes differently from x,t .)

In particular if one has a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$, then from the point of view of a moving frame, this particle has rest mass with kinetic energy (which may be possibly combined into an overall energy term which is not just kinetic energy), velocity = x/t and momentum. In other words there seems to be a physical example which gives motivation to having (x,t) and (p,E) transform in the same manner. In the Galilean case, x and t transform in one way and the authors of (1) suggest $v1$ (the velocity in the x,t frame) transforms as $v1-v$ i.e in another way.

Given the above, instead of using $t=t'$ as in the Galilean case, one may generalize to $t'=g(v)t$. Then $x'/t' = v$ implies that $x'=vg(v)t$ for this same $x=0$ scenario. One may then postulate the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ t' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} g & -vg \\ -vg & g \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ t \end{pmatrix} \quad ((3)) \quad \text{One may replace } x,t \text{ with } p,E \text{ and the same with the (') values.}$$

Then:

$$-Et + px = gg p'x' - vv ggp'x' + vvgg E't' - gg E't' \quad ((4))$$

This implies that $g = \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ where b is a constant to make v/b be dimensionless. Applying this example to light yields $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

One also finds that E and p are no longer $.5mv1v1$ and $mv1$, but are now $mobb/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ and $p=Ev1$ where $v1$ is the velocity in the x,t frame.

Thus the Lorentz transformation follows (without the specific value of b which from other arguments becomes c i.e. applying the transformation to light). Thus one is able to see why the Galilean transformation is not suitable, even in a nonrelativistic classical scenario.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the work of (1) in which it is shown that the combination of the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation for a free particle together with a Galilean transformation leads to: $W'(x',t') = W(x,t) \exp(\text{phase factor})$. The authors then argue that the phase factor is a remnant of special relativity. They go on to show that even in nonrelativistic classical mechanics the Hamilton Jacobi equation $H(x, dS/dx) + dS/dt (\text{partial}) = 0$ implies that $S'(x',t') = S(x(x',t'), t(t')) + \text{extra terms}$. We show how these extra terms may arise in a different manner from (1) which does not require explicitly that v_1 (the velocity in the x, t frame) transform as $v_1 - v$ and consider how a generalization of the Galilean transformation, namely the Lorentz transformation yields $-Et + px$ the same as $-E't' + p'x'$. We explicitly use $S = -Et + px$ for a free particle in our analysis. This leads to the idea of this quantity being a dot product and shows why the Galilean transformation is inadequate to make $S'(x',t') = S(x(x',t'), t(t'), E(E',p'), p(E',p'))$.

References

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